

REINFORCED PLASTICS IN RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES - THE INDIAN SCENE

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ABSTRACT

In a primarily agrarian country like India, one of the major constraints has been the shortage of required energy inputs. To combat this, there has been a constant search for new and renewable sources of energy. Biogas and Wind Energy are some of the fruits of the constant search for new sources of energy while DAP (Draught Animal Power) continues to be a conventional renewable source of energy.

The Research & Development Centre of our Company has carried out considerable amount of pioneering work in the successful promotion of fibre glass reinforced plastics (hereafter referred to as RP in the paper) in the field of renewable energy through design, development and testing of prototypes of the following :

- * Animal Drawn Vehicles
- * Wind Mills
- * Biogas Plants

The paper highlights the work carried out by our Company in the development of the concept of using RP in the applications mentioned above.

INTRODUCTION

The Government of India has been actively promoting development of renewable energy sources since 1981. This development received an impetus with the setting up of the Department of Non-Conventional Energy Sources (DNES) by the Government in 1982. For most of devices used for harnessing renewable energy such as biogas, DAP and wind energy; carbon steel or wood (as the case may be) has been used as the traditional material of construction. However, problems were encountered during use of these devices in continuous service; such as low operation efficiency, poor corrosion resistance, frequent maintenance, longer transportation and installation times etc. The Research and Development Centre of our Company took up the task of overcoming these problems by modification of the existing designs in each case to suit their development in RP; so as to result in greater efficiency of operation, nil maintenance and hence, longer life.

RP IN ANIMAL DRAWN VEHICLES

Animal Drawn Vehicles (ADV) appear to be on the decline in most developing countries excepting India and China, where they still continue to play a critical role. The most popular form of ADV is drawn by bulls. These are mainly used for transporting sugar cane, fertilizer, grain, timber etc. The following components constitute an ADV :

- * Body
- * Yoke
- * Pull Beam

- * Driver 's Seat
- * Axle
- * Wheels (Pneumatic Tyres/Wood)

Conventional ADVs use wood/carbon steel as the main material of construction. Warping of the wood due to seasonal variations results in frequent maintenance of conventional ADVs. Moreover, the high tare weight places restrictions on the payload, which can not exceed 3 - 3.5 Tons during practical use. The development of ADVs in RP was taken up with a view to minimise tare weight and achieve higher payload. Our Company has successfully designed ADVs in RP for payloads of 1.5, 2.5 and 4 Tons suitable for use with

- * Pneumatic Tyres
- * Conventional wooden wheels with carbon steel rims

For the various payload capacities mentioned above, design studies were made in each case in order to arrive at the following critical parameters :

- * Dimensions and Positioning of stiffeners in longitudinal and transverse directions
- * Optimum economical thickness of RP

The RP body of the ADVs were made by contact moulding. The body, yoke, driver's seat and pull beam were made separately and then assembled. The fitment of the RP body on the axle was taken care of by provision of adequate carbon steel inserts in the RP body at the points of mounting the body on the axle. Assembly of the body to axle was carried out using bolts and nuts. Extensive field trials with varying payloads were carried out on the different models using both pneumatic tyres and conventional wooden wheels depending on the case (see Figures 1 & 2). The successful field trials on all the models resulted in the concept of using RP for ADVs catching on rapidly in India, in both rural and urban sectors. The main advantages of ADVs fabricated in RP can be summed up as follows:

- * Reduced tare weight (upto 30%) and increased payload (upto 20-25%) which make it more remunerative to the enduser
- * Hauling of the vehicles on steep incline and uneven terrain is achieved with minimum effort by the animals due to lower tare weight
- * Better manoeuvrability of the vehicle in view of lower tare weight and reduced slippage
- * Negligible maintenance as problems of warping etc., are eliminated
- * Better aesthetics as RP can be pigmented in various shades

In spite of the higher initial cost, ADVs made in RP have become increasingly popular in view of the enduser realising higher earnings per trip because of the increased payload capacity.

WIND MILL ROTOR

The installation of wind mills for minor irrigation (primarily for pumping water) was taken up by the Department of Non-Conventional Energy Sources in 1982-83.

The wind mill used for minor irrigation essentially consists of a rotor (consisting of 12 blades) mounted on a frame. Circular motion of the rotor is converted to reciprocating motion through a main horizontal shaft, crank, connecting rod, wooden cross piston head and pump rod. The pump is a single acting, reciprocating type piston pump. Water delivery occurs during the upward stroke of the piston.

In order to overcome the problem of corrosion of the carbon steel rotor (especially in coastal areas) and also to increase the efficiency of operation of wind mills, the development of the frame and blades in RP was taken up. The inner and outer rings of the frame, blades, support angles and hub were all designed and developed in RP. The components were made by contact moulding using isophthalic unsaturated polyester resin. The use of RP for the rotor frame and blades resulted in a weight saving of approximately 30% compared to carbon steel. Field trials on the prototypes were conducted and the wind mills have been performing satisfactorily till date and found to withstand cyclonic weather conditions very effectively (see Figure 3).

The rotor velocity (and hence water discharge) depends on the wind velocity. Thus, with a lighter frame work, the rotor velocity is appreciable even at low wind velocities, leading to significant discharge of water. The lighter weight also results in lesser starting torque and in the wind mill being operational even at low wind velocities (in the range of 4 - 6 km per hour). Considerable discharge of water thus results even at low wind velocities. With carbon steel rotor frame, water discharge occurs only at a minimum wind velocity of 9 - 10 km per hour.

The successful field trials has resulted in the ready acceptance of use of RP as a material of construction for the rotor because of the following advantages :

- * Reduced starting torque
- * Reduced weight, resulting in greater efficiency - since water can be pumped even at low wind speeds
- * Negligible maintenance due to lesser wear on moving mechanical components
- * Better aerodynamic design
- * Freedom from corrosion
- * Longer life

BIOGAS PLANTS

Biogas is a low cost feasible source of fuel in India and is obtained by the anaerobic digestion of live stock excrement, agricultural waste, sewage sludge non-edible oil cakes etc. Biogas generated from cattle dung (Gobar) is known as "Gobar Gas" and is the most popular source of biogas in India. The biogas holders are rated by the amount of gas generated in cubic meters per day. The popular family type biogas plants are 3, 4, 6, 8 and 10 cu.met. capacity. The biogas plant consists mainly of the gas holder and digester.

The development of the entire gas holder in RP (which involved total elimination of carbon steel including that used in the structural frame work) was taken up in 1983. Since a minimum weight of the gas holder was required to maintain a pressure of 7.5 - 10 cms. of water column; adequate stiffeners were provided on the roof portion of the RP holder to take the additional dead load (in the form of sand bags, bricks etc) to compensate for the lower weight in RP (see Figures 4 & 5). The use of RP yielded a weight saving of more than 75%. The other advantages were :

- * Nil corrosion
- * Faster installation
- * Higher biogas generation irrespective of climatic variations

Our Company has recently designed and developed the digester also in RP for plants upto 6 M³ capacity.

CONCLUSIONS

The successful applications of RP in the areas mentioned above have proved to be a big boost to the RP industry in India. It is hoped that in the years to come, RP will open up new vistas for its use in other forms of renewable energy.

The author of this manuscript is a Research & Development Engineer from a manufacturing unit in India.

Fig. 1 ADV made in RP with conventional wooden wheels

Fig. 2
Field trials on ADV (in RP)
with pneumatic tyres

Fig. 3
Wind mill made in
RP in operation

Fig. 4
RP biogas holder
(view of stiffeners)

Fig. 5
RP biogas holder in
installed condition